

Comment on “Statistical review of A Trial of Lopinavir-Ritonavir in Adults Hospitalized with Severe Covid-19 by B. Cao et al” by Gates S, Emsley R, Dahly D

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This statistical review [1] provides a critique of the statistical aspects of the recently published trial of Lopinavir-Ritonavir in Adults Hospitalized with Severe Covid-19 [2]. While the review contains some comments that I agree with (and naturally others I agree with less), I was rather taken back to read the recommendation that an ordinal regression approach should be used to analyse the outcome in this trial.

My concern with the recommendation is based on three points, each of which I will detail below.

Timing of analysis

A typical ordinal regression approach will consider the change in the number of patients in each category between baseline and one specific time point. In the context of the ordinal scale used in the trial, there are two terminal states: death or recovery and eventually all patients will end up in either of these, regardless of the intervention that the patient receives. Consequently, if the time point for analysis is chosen too late, there is limited ability to detect any effect (or even none at all if the treatment, for example, does not impact mortality). Similarly, if the timing is too early, at a point where any difference is yet to emerge, an existing effect will not be detectable.

Hence such an analysis is deeply dependent on the timing of the analysis. As primary analyses of clinical trials are to be pre-determined, data exploration to identify the “correct” timing once data are available is not acceptable. Given the limited knowledge about the natural history of the disease, the corresponding impact of the treatment on the distribution of the number of patients in each category of the ordinal scale and the heterogeneity in patient course of illness, fixing the right time point therefore is, more or less, a wild guess with potentially dire consequences on statistical power.

Disregard of time

In the context of a pandemic where a key concern is exceeding the capacity of the health system, reductions in time spent in hospital, time on ventilation and the like are crucially important. The proposed analysis method does not take this into account despite the relevant information being readily available.

I note that this point is mentioned in the review itself, yet completely ignored in the recommendation of analysis method.

It is also worth noting, that the time-to-event endpoint does not strictly dichotomize to a binary outcome as suggested in the review, but rather captures the time element. In other words, the ordinal regression approach can have efficiency gains relative to a binary endpoint, but it fails to capture the time course of recovery. The relative trade-off in statistical power will depend on the underlying model. In the case of Covid-19, the varied time-course of recovery (ranging from less than a week to over a month), argues for analyses that will capture time.

Interpretation and other issues

The proposed analysis requires the reader to be able to interpret an odd-ratios – a task that I would argue even trained statisticians sometimes struggle with. How missing data should be dealt with is also unclear given that this information is likely informative.

On the basis of the above, I believe that using an ordinal regression approach to analyse an outcome such as the one in this trial, should *not* be recommended for Covid-19. Finally, I want to make the point that I believe that there are definitely other statistical analysis methods, such as a Fine-Gray competing risk approach [3], that could have been useful in the analysis of this trial, but I do not believe that the recommended ordinal regression approach is amongst them.

References

- [1] Simon Gates, Richard Emsley, and Darren Dahly. Statistical review of A Trial of Lopinavir–Ritonavir in Adults Hospitalized with Severe Covid-19 by B. Cao et al (Version 1.0), 2020. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3746512>.
- [2] Bin Cao, Yeming Wang, Danning Wen, Wen Liu, Jingli Wang, Guohui Fan, Lianguo Ruan, Bin Song, Yanping Cai, Ming Wei, et al. A Trial of Lopinavir–Ritonavir in Adults Hospitalized with Severe Covid-19. *New England Journal of Medicine*, 2020.
- [3] Jason P Fine and Robert J Gray. A proportional hazards model for the subdistribution of a competing risk. *Journal of the American Statistical Association*, 94(446):496–509, 1999.